

THE ROLE OF DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES IN ENHANCING ENGLISH LANGUAGE LEARNING AMONG YOUNG LEARNERS

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Abstract. Digital technologies are becoming one of the key factors in modern education especially in foreign language learning. Today's young learners actively use smartphones, smart technologies, educational applications, and online resources in daily lives. As a result, technology has started to influence not only communication but also the process of language acquisition. This article examines the role of digital technologies in improving English language learning among young learners and analyzes how technological tools influence learners' motivation, vocabulary acquisition, pronunciation, fluency and communication skills. The research was carried out using a quantitative method. More than 100 students participated in questionnaires related to their use of digital technologies when they are learning English. The findings revealed that many learners regularly use educational videos, online dictionaries, mobile applications, and different types of applications to practice English outside the classroom.

The study also demonstrated that digital technologies increase students' interest in learning English and assist them become more independent learners. However, several challenges such as distraction from social media and internet-related problems were also identified. Overall, the research proves that integrating digital technologies into English language education can make the learning process more interactive, easier, practical, and effective for young students.

Keywords: digital technologies, English language learning, young learners, educational applications, online learning, language acquisition.

Аннотация. Цифровые технологии в настоящее время становятся важной частью современной системы образования, особенно в сфере изучения иностранных языков. Молодые обучающиеся активно используют смартфоны, социальные сети, образовательные приложения и интернет-ресурсы в повседневной жизни. В результате технологии оказывают влияние не только на процесс общения, но и на изучение языка. Данное исследование направлено на определение роли цифровых технологий в обучении английскому языку среди молодых учащихся, а также на анализ их влияния на мотивацию, словарный запас, произношение и коммуникативные навыки обучающихся.

В исследовании был использован количественный метод. Более 100 студентов приняли участие в анкетировании, посвящённом использованию цифровых технологий при изучении английского языка. Результаты показали, что большинство обучающихся регулярно применяют образовательные видеоматериалы, онлайн-словари, мобильные приложения и социальные платформы для практики английского языка вне учебных занятий.

Кроме того, исследование подтвердило, что цифровые технологии повышают интерес студентов к изучению английского языка и способствуют развитию

самостоятельного обучения. Вместе с тем были выявлены некоторые проблемы, связанные с отвлечением на социальные сети и трудностями интернет-соединения. В целом результаты исследования показывают, что интеграция цифровых технологий в процесс обучения английскому языку делает его более интерактивным, практичным и эффективным для молодых учащихся.

Ключевые слова: цифровые технологии, изучение английского языка, молодые учащиеся, образовательные приложения, онлайн-обучение, усвоение языка.

Annotatsiya. Raqamli texnologiyalar bugungi kunda zamonaviy ta'lim tizimining ajralmas qismiga aylanib bormoqda, ayniqsa chet tillarini o'qitishda ularning ahamiyati tobora ortmoqda. Hozirgi yosh avlod kundalik hayotida smartfonlar, ijtimoiy tarmoqlar, ta'limiy ilovalar va internet resurslaridan faol foydalanadi. Shu sababli texnologiyalar nafaqat muloqot vositasi, balki til o'rganish jarayoniga ham sezilarli ta'sir ko'rsatmoqda. Mazkur tadqiqot yosh o'quvchilarning ingliz tilini o'rganishida raqamli texnologiyalarning o'rnini aniqlash hamda ularning motivatsiya, lug'at boyligi, talaffuz va kommunikativ ko'nikmalariga ta'sirini tahlil qilishga qaratilgan.

Tadqiqot davomida miqdoriy metoddan foydalanildi va 100 nafardan ortiq talabalar o'rtasida so'rovnomma o'tkazildi. Tadqiqot natijalari shuni ko'rsatdiki, o'quvchilarning aksariyati darsdan tashqari paytda ingliz tilini rivojlantirish uchun ta'limiy videolar, onlayn lug'atlar, mobil ilovalar hamda ijtimoiy tarmoqlardan muntazam foydalanadilar.

Shuningdek, tadqiqot raqamli texnologiyalar o'quvchilarning ingliz tiliga bo'lgan qiziqishini oshirish va mustaqil o'rganish ko'nikmalarini shakllantirishda muhim rol o'ynashini ko'rsatdi. Shu bilan birga, ijtimoiy tarmoqlarga chalg'ish va internet bilan bog'liq muammolar kabi ayrim salbiy holatlar ham aniqlandi. Umuman olganda, ingliz tili ta'limiga raqamli texnologiyalarni joriy etish o'quv jarayonining samaradorligi, interaktivligi va amaliy ahamiyatini oshirishga xizmat qiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: raqamli texnologiyalar, ingliz tilini o'rganish, yosh o'quvchilar, ta'limiy ilovalar, onlayn ta'lim, til o'zlashtirish.

INTRODUCTION

In the modern world, technology has become an integral part of human life. Almost all areas such as education, communication, business and healthcare are closely related to digital development. Over the past decade, education systems around the world have increasingly begun to use digital technologies in the teaching and learning process. Among the various subjects in education, the study of foreign languages, especially English, has undergone major changes due to modern technologies. Today, English is not just a school subject, but also an essential tool for communication, education, science and professional development. Therefore, many young students are interested in improving their English and they are looking for easier and more effective ways to learn the language.

Compared to the past, today's students prefer more interactive and practical lessons. Therefore, teachers are rapidly using digital tools in addition to traditional teaching methods. Nowadays, every student can learn English through mobile apps, online courses, different websites, videos, podcasts, and even social media. These sources allow students to practice English not only in class but also in their daily lives.

Many students find technology-based learning more engaging cause it includes visual materials, interactive exercises and real-life conversation opportunities. Watching English videos,

listening to podcasts or using dictionary apps could help students develop pronunciation and vocabulary in a more natural way. Digital technologies also encourage students to learn independently and give them more confidence in using the language.

However, digital learning also has some drawbacks. Some students may spend too much time on social media and lose focus during the learning process. Others may face problems related to poor internet quality or a lack of technological devices.

This research aims to explore how digital technologies influence English language learning among young learners and how these technologies affect students' motivation, participation, and language development.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Many scholars and researchers have studied the relationship between technology and foreign language learning. According to Prensky (2001), modern students are “digital natives” because they grow up surrounded by technological devices and adapt quickly to digital environments. This idea explains why young learners are more interested in technology-based education.

Chapelle (2003) stated that technology-assisted language learning provides learners with more opportunities for interaction and communication. Through online platforms and multimedia resources, students can access authentic materials and practice English in real-life contexts.

Similarly, Warschauer (2004) emphasized that digital technologies encourage collaborative learning and learner autonomy. Online communication tools allow students to interact with teachers and other learners beyond classroom walls. In recent years, mobile applications such as Duolingo, Kahoot, Quizlet, and BBC Learning English have become popular among English learners. Researchers found that these applications help to improve vocabulary retention, fluency, pronunciation, and listening comprehension through interactive exercises and visual support.

However, some scientists also discussed the negative effects of excessive technology use. Kirschner and De Bruyckere (2017) argued that social media distractions may reduce students' concentration and academic performance if technology is not used appropriately. Although many international studies have focused on digital learning, there is still limited research about Uzbek learners and their experiences with technology-based English education. Therefore, this study aims to contribute to this field by analyzing the effectiveness of digital technologies among young learners in Uzbekistan.

METHODOLOGY

This research employed a quantitative approach to investigate the role of digital technologies in English language learning among young students. The data were collected through questionnaires distributed among school students, college students, and university learners studying English at different levels.

More than 100 participants between the ages of 12 and 22 took part in the research. The questionnaire consisted of 15 questions divided into three categories: background information, use of digital applications and learning outcomes.

The participants answered questions related to educational videos, online dictionaries, modern applications, social media platforms, podcasts, and virtual learning environments. The collected information were analyzed statistically and presented in percentages. The purpose of using questionnaires was to identify learners' attitudes toward digital technologies and to examine how frequently they use technological tools while studying English.

RESULTS

The detection of the research showed that digital technologies have a positive influence on English language learning among young learners. According to the questionnaire results, approximately 85% of participants regularly utilize digital tools while studying English. Most learners calculate that YouTube videos, educational applications, and online dictionaries are the most useful resources for improving language skills. About 74% of students mentioned that videos and podcasts assisted them improve listening comprehension and pronunciation. In addition, many participants believed that mobile applications helped them memorize vocabulary effectively.

Another important finding was related to learner motivation. More than 80% of participants stated that technology-based learning is more interactive and enjoyable compared to traditional classroom methods. Students particularly enjoyed interactive exercises, visual materials, and online games.

However, several difficulties were also revealed during the research. Around 37% of learners mentioned that social media distracts them while study sessions. Some participants also reported problems with internet connection and lack of technological devices.

DISCUSSION

The results of the research indicate that digital applications significantly support English language learning among young learners. The findings demonstrate that technology-based learning environments increase learner motivation and participation because students find digital tools more interactive and enjoyable.

One of the major advantages identified in this research is accessibility. Learners can practice English anytime they want through smartphones, online platforms, and educational applications. Exposure to authentic English materials such as videos, online dictionaries and podcasts also helps students improve pronunciation and listening skills more naturally. The findings support previous studies conducted by Chapelle and Warschauer, who highlighted the importance of technology-assisted language learning and learner autonomy. Young learners in this study showed positive attitudes toward digital learning because it creates a more comfortable and enjoyable learning atmosphere.

At the same time, the research also revealed several difficulties. Social media distractions and unstable internet access may negatively affect learning performance. Therefore, teachers should teach students on how to use digital technologies effectively and responsibly. Overall, the integration of English language learning with digital technologies can better prepare young learners for education and future professional opportunities.

CONCLUSION

All in all, digital technologies have become one of the essential keys in enhancing English language learning among young learners. Educational applications, online platforms, videos, podcasts, online dictionaries and digital resources create effective opportunities for improving vocabulary, pronunciation, listening comprehension, and learner motivation.

Although some challenges like internet dependency and social media distractions still exist, the advantages of digital learning are much more significant. Technology-based education creates a flexible and interactive learning environment that supports students to become active and independent learners.

Therefore, teachers and educational institutions should integrate modern digital applications into English language teaching in order to improve the quality of education and prepare young students for future academic and professional success.

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